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D6.2.3 - Report on CO₂ emissions during stationary phase of microbes (soil basal respiration rate)

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Based on the workflow of the AGROECOseqC, these deliverables were programmed in Task 6.2: Microbial C-respiration dynamic and mitigation of greenhouse gas emission (leader: Flavio Fornasier - CREA-VE).

Report on CO₂ emissions during stationary phase of microbes of samples from core sites

Objective - The objective of this task was to assess the effect of considered management practices in AGROECOseqC on soil CO₂ emissions during the stationary phase of soil microbiota, corresponding to the soil basal respiration rate. The soil respiration tests were performed on soil collected at two moment of plant demand (MAX and MIN), with the aim to measure the microbial activity (soil basal respiration):

- at the moment of minimum competition between plants and soil microbiota (MIN);
- at the moment of maximum competition for water and nutrient resources between plants and soil microbiota (MAX).

Soil sampling and methodology - A total of n. 300 soil samples (Experiment A and Experiment B), collected from the nine core sites (CS1-IT, CS2-FR₁, CS3-FR₂, CS4-DK, CS5-ES, CS6-NL, CS7-LT, CS8 -TK and CS9-BE) identified at the beginning of the project, were processed at the CREA-VE in Gorizia (Italy). In Table 1, the list of agronomic practices applied in each core-site are reported.

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Table 1. Description of agronomic practices (T1, T2, T3-control) applied in the nine AGROECOseqC core-sites.

	Treatments	Code
S1 (CREA, Italy)	Compost, no tillage, spontaneous cover	T1
	Compost, tillage, mixed cover crops	T2
	BAU - tillage, organic fertilizer, no CC (Control)	T3
CS2 (INRAE - CF)	Grasses, legumes - new system	T1
	Spring wheat, grasses, legumes - new system	T2
	Spring wheat - new system (Control)	T3
CS3 (INRAE -MP)	Tree strip + perennial grass, no tillage	T2
	Crop rotation in agroforestry alley, tillage (Control)	T3
CS4 (AU)	Lolium perenne and white clover	T1
	Six-species mixture	T2
	Lolium perenne (Control)	T3
CS5 (CSIC-INIA)	No tillage, wheat	T1
	No tillage, rotation (wheat-vetch-barley)	T2
	Minimum tillage, wheat (Control)	T3
CS6 (WUR)	Vetch + Oat	T1
	Vetch + Oat + Radish	T2
	Fallow (Control)	T3
CS7 (LAMMC)	No tillage without cover crops	T1
	No tillage + cover crops	T2
	Conventional tillage without cover crops (Control)	T3
CS8 (TAGEM)	No fungi inoculum with cover crop	T1
	Fungi inoculum with cover crop	T2
	No fungi inoculum without cover crop (Control)	T3
CS9 (CRAW)	Sugar beet, wheat, barley, farmyard manure	T1
	Sugar beet, wheat, barley, crop res. restitution and cover crop	T2
	Sugar beet, wheat, barley, residue exportation (Control)	T3

In each core-site, 100 g of each soil samples were collected in field in two moments: at minimum plant demand (MIN) and at maximum plant demand (MAX), as described in the AGROECOseqC Handbook. In Experiment A, T1 and T2 treatments, at increasing level of agroecological intensification (T2>T1), were compared to T3 as control treatment (no agroecological intensification, or business as usual). Per each treatment, in each of the four blocks, four elementary samples were collected to form one composite one (3 treatments x 4 blocks = 12 composite samples/core-site).

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In Experiment B, T1 and T2 treatments, at increasing level of agroecological intensification (T2>T1), were compared. Per each treatment, in three blocks only, three elementary samples were collected and maintained separated to consider soil spatial effect (2 treatments x 3 blocks x 3 replicates/blocks = 18 samples/core-site). All the soil samples were sent to CREA-VE by each partner between September 2022 and October 2023 by refrigerated shipment and stored at -20 °C until processing, following the protocols defined in the AGROECOseqC Handbook.

Sample processing started June 2023 and terminated in June 2024.

The CO₂ emissions were quantified as following: the received frozen soil samples were first put in refrigerator a 4°C for two days to allow them to thaw slowly and sieved at 2 mm and checked for water content determination. Then they were conditioned at 40% of water holding capacity (WHC) and left for two days at room temperature (25°C), to monitor the CO₂ efflux rates on time without altering microclimate inside the measurement chamber.

50 grams of soil (dry basis) were put in small polypropylene mesh (100 mm) bags (Figure 1) which, in turn, were allocated in boxes and put in thermostat at 25°C at 100% relative humidity for preventing desiccation (soil incubation).

Figure 1. Soil sample in 100 mm-polypropylene mesh bags.

The measurement of CO₂ emission started 2 days after incubation at 25°C and performed every three days. After 8-11 days from the incubation start, a constant emission rate was reached, and basal respiration was therefore quantified (in $\mu\text{gC g}_{\text{soil}}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$).

The device used for AGROECOseqC measurements is shown in Figure 2.

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Figure 2. Device used by CREA-VE to measure CO₂ emission from soil samples.

Each sample to be measured was taken from thermostat and equilibrated at 380 ppm/vol CO₂ for 10 minutes, then put in measurement chamber and emission rate recorded for 10 minutes.

A typical emission curve is reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Example of dynamic curve of CO₂ concentration evolved from soil sample in 1 hour (in ppm).

The CO₂ emission rate (as soil basal respiration rate) was calculated, according to Delle Vedove et al. (2007). This measurement allows to evaluate the soil microbial basal respiration after reaching the stationary state, thus giving an indication of the soil attitude to fast or slowly mineralize organic

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substrates in soil, as affected by agroecological management practices (T1 and T2), compared to T3 (control).

Results and discussion - When all the analysis were completed, the final dataset for soil basal respiration (CO_2 emission rate, in $\mu\text{gC g}_{\text{soil}}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) was submitted for following data analysis (M6.2.1). A first, preliminary descriptive evaluation is reported in Figure 4. Per each core-sites, the histograms represent the CO_2 emission rate in function of the applied agronomic practices (T1, T2 and T3-control), recorded at the minimum and maximum demand of nutrients by the plant species (crops/cover crops/prairie) coexisting in each studied agroecosystem.

Figure 4. CO_2 emission rate (in $\mu\text{gC g}_{\text{soil}}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) registered in all the core-sites, as affected by the agroecological treatments (T1 and T2), compared to control (T3). Soil samples were collected at nutrient minimum plant demand (MIN, in grey) and maximum plant demand (MAX, in green). Different letters represent significant differences (Tukey HSD test for mean comparison). Statistical difference at $p \leq 0.05$.

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Results shows a significant difference of CO₂ emission rate in all the core-sites, except in CS4 (DK) and CS6 (NL). In CS1, the highest rate of soil respiration was recorded at MIN-T2 samples (fallow, before CC sowing) and the lowest one at MAX-T2, when CC were introduced. In CS2, as expected the CO₂ emission rate was higher at MAX sampling, while the minimum recorded value was at MIN-T2, where plant diversity was the highest one among T1, T2 and T3. In CS3, the soil respiration rate decreases significantly in T2, both at MIN and MAX, probably due to the soil no tillage, compared to tillage in T3 (tilled control). No effects were observed in CS4 and CS6, while in CS5 the lowest CO₂ emission rate was in T1 and T3 at MIN plant demand: here, the introduction of vetch and barley in the wheat rotation apparently increased the SOM mineralization compared to the wheat monocropping, regardless the soil no tillage vs minimum tillage factor. In CS7 and CS8, the sampling moment made the difference, being highest the soil respiration rate at MIN plant demand, corresponding to the fallow (before sowing), regardless the tested agroecological practices. In CS9, at MIN plant demand the lowest CO₂ emission rate was found in T1, where cover crops were not introduced in field and farmyard manure was applied.

Conclusions - At the end, the introduced agronomic practices played a role on affecting soil basal respiration rate (as CO₂ emission) in function, of the sampling moment. We remark that the system diversity (plant species in field with associated soil microbiota) and the applied agronomic practices made the difference in recorded results, giving not always the same trend when comparing the considered AGROECOseqC experimental sites.

JUSTIFICATION - Although a delay in completing it, on the end of August 2024 the D6.2.1 was concluded, whilst D6.2.2 did not, due instrumental problems: in particular, this issue emerged after the unavailability of the old respirometer at CREA VE, needed for performing the planned analysis. A new respirometric system was necessary, but the AGROECOseqC budget was not planned to cover this new acquisition. CREA-VE charged completely the costs for analysis using an IRGA system (Infrared Gas Analyzer), following method described by Delle Vedove et al. (2007). Some unforeseen problems during the new setup delayed the onset of respiration tests. In addition, the high number of

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samples of core sites to be processed in AGROECOseqC and the overlap with other laboratory EJP Soil activities, further delayed the completion. However, as the analysis of the CO₂ emission during stationary phase was completed and dataset, required for the interpretation of soil C emissions rate in sampled soils, was made available to allow their proper statistical evaluation.

Note on D6.2.2: Report on C emissions after substrate addition

Regarding the D6.2.2, CREA cannot guarantee the dataset on C emissions after substrate addition due to the delay in equipment availability, and consequently this deliverable was deleted from the AGROECOseqC deliverable list in the last Continuous reporting action (Feb-Sept. 2024).

References

Delle Vedove G., Alberti G., Zuliani M., Peressotti A., Inghima I., Zerbi G.. 2017. Automated Monitoring of Soil Respiration: an Improved Automatic Chamber System. *Ital. J. Agron. / Riv. Agron.*, 2007, 4:377-382

Attachments

M6.2.1_AGROECOseqC_Soil basal respiration rate dataset